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Leveraging Social Inclusion Through the Impact of Customer Services Quality on Organizational Performance at a Selected Commercial Bank in Namibia*

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Abstract

This paper investigated the impact of customer services quality on the organizational performance at a selected commercial Bank in Namibia as a social inclusion driver for economic growth within the banking sector. The objectives for the study were: to establish the relationship between quality customer service and organizational performance; to establish the impact of quality customer service on the overall organizational performance and to offer recommendations to the management and relevant stakeholders. A quantitative research approach was used with a simple random probability sampling. A closed-ended questionnaire was used to collect data to leverage social inclusion through the impact of customer services quality on the overall organizational performance. 57 Closed ended-questionnaires were used to collect the data. By using descriptive statistics, data were recorded on excel spreadsheets. The results of the study were presented by using graphs and converting the data into percentage, mean values and percentages. The finding reveals that quality customer service contributes mostly towards an improved organisational performance. The results further established that majority of the clients including the customer service consultants' staff strongly agreed that, quality customer service contributes to the sustainable organizational performance. The study recommends to the top management of a selected commercial bank to keep on investing in the customer service quality by increasing the numbers of ATMs at every business centre in the area as it provides convenient alternatives to the customers. Furthermore, investments in technological innovations and customer service help commercial banks to sustainably retain and attract more customers yielding much-needed profitability for the bank. The study recommends that future researchers should investigate the inclusive sustainability of customer services quality and how they affect the overall organizational performance at different commercial banks.

Key Words: *commercial bank, Namibia, organisational, performance, Sustainable quality service,*

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the Problem

Namibia like many other countries in Southern Africa is working toward gaining a good reputation in the world with regard to its governance. However its governance machinery still needs to be lubricated further to enhance

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service delivery for the betterment of Namibian people. The Government has adopted a national development plan⁵ that aimed at strengthening institutions for effective service delivery to people in line with sustainable social inclusion (NDP5 report, 2017).

Annual customer satisfaction survey by the business community is recognized that service delivery is not only a challenge in the public sector. It was therefore agreed that in the true Harambee spirit, the Namibia Chamber of Commerce and Industry (NCCI) would on an annual basis measure customer satisfaction in the business sector. During the Harambee Prosperity Plan consultations, the NCCI undertook to develop sector-based targets on turnaround time in the private sector. Effective governance is not only essential but is a pre-condition for the government to facilitate sustainable development. Without effective governance, there can be no sustained economic development, job creation, and poverty reduction. While we have strong governance architecture, it is noted that more should be done to strengthen governance and improve on service delivery through the national objective project of The HARAMBEE PLAN FOR PROSPERITY [HPP] which has been developed to complement the National Development Plans and Vision 2030. The HPP is a focused and targeted approach to achieve high impact in defined priority areas. One of the agreed upon features of planning is that it must be flexible (Harambee Plan for Prosperity 2016/2017&2019/20).

Like many other private institutions, commercial banks in Namibia and the world at large, the Selected Bank in this study has invested much in improving customer service as a key strategy in achieving its mission of creating a better world for all in Namibia and more particularly to compliment the Governments' Harambee Prosperity Plan and respond to the prevailing market demand by identifying the impact of quality customer service and the return that justify investments in customer service. In that connection, the selected bank has come up with what is called 4s strategies focusing on the followings: People, Planet, Partnership and Profit as a vehicle to take the bank to the expected quality customer service standard that subsequently leads to profit growth. These key strategies suggest that, when you have right people at the right positions, that understand the environment where they operate from and the importance of keeping our planet safe, the bank will be able to attract good partnership that will help grow the business to make profit and that will be driven by the people strategy to provide quality customer service (the selected Bank Business Plan 2014/2016).

1.2 Explore Importance of the Problem

Wilson, Zeithamal, Bitner & Gremler (2012:5) stated that all economic activities whose output is not a physical product or construction, is generally consumed at the time it is produced, and provides added value in forms such as convenience, amusement, timeliness, comfort or health that are essentially intangible concerns of its first purchaser.

Despite the government s' Harambee Plan for Prosperity call to all private and public institutions to support the national development goals by investing in customer service quality, the selected bank has recorded 267 complaints about the quality of customer service between the year 2013 to 2016 and this information is recorded in the customer comment book which is the source of this information. In addition there has been an outcry from the general public about the quality of customer service at the selected bank Branches and this information came through different channel of media such as The Namibian Newspapers SMS page, Social media, Customer comment Book, National and Indigenous language Radio Station between the months of April 2013 to April 2016, more complaints have been aired. During the year 2014, feedback forms were implemented by the bank to assist customers by giving them a platform to rate the services of the bank. Most issues raised by the customers include long queues, long waiting time, rude personnel and lack of queue management. And what did the bank do so far to address these issues? The bank has created online link known as Customer Service First where all comments and complaints can be lodged on for future reference, in addition, the introduction of e-educators in the branch to teach incoming customer on the use of electronic banking facilities that supposed to reduce the preserved service failures of long queues which brought customer complaints, however, there is not much difference and no change in the customer complaints. Other clients recommended the bank to work on their customer service as the way forward to retain existing clients. Based on the number of complaints the management has decided to find out what has really caused the complaints since they tried to improve by introducing e-educators, that is supposed to direct the customer queue and teach them how to use electronic

banking and there seems to be no change in customer's complains, hence this investigation is necessary to reveal the real problem.

1.3 Describe Relevant Quality Service Issues

Cook (2011:18) stated that, as the power of the customer increases, consumers are becoming more vocal in expressing their dissatisfaction. As the vast majority of customers still do complain, they give the company both valuable insights and the opportunity to improve the quality of customer service. Yet many organizations still do not actively encourage complaints. In the United Kingdom, the regulatory body for the financial services industry, the Financial Services Authority, is trying to buck this trend by spearheading an initiative called Treating Customers Fairly; which sets out guidelines for dealing with complaints. This provides a definition of a complaint as an expression of dissatisfaction. It promotes the benefits of effective complaint handling which include improved customer retention and avoidance of unfavourable publicity.

On the other hand, Wilson, et al. (2012:79) suggested that customers do not perceive quality in a one-dimensional way but rather judge quality based on multiple factors relevant to the context. The dimensions of service quality have been identified through the pioneering research of Parasuraman, Zenithal, and Berry (2012). Their research identified five specific digestions of service quality that apply across a variety of service context. These dimensions represent how customers organize information about service quality in their minds that have also triggered by fast movement of global information. The customer gets comparable information from a different source of information as the researchers have indicated in the introduction, fast-moving information has a potential to increase the customer complaints.

The perception that banking services are generally characterized by poor customer service is attributed to the lack of customer understanding of the dynamics that made up the banking operations, the regulations governing the banking services, while on the other hand, banks are not taking the challenges of customer education more seriously to make them (customers) understand the use of technology and management planning, ineffective use of electronic banking facilities, sufficient customer area to accommodate the overwhelming demand of services. On the other hand, customer compares services in different areas with that one in the cities. Researchers observed that, since 2015, there has been a long queue of customers waiting for either cash withdrawal or cash deposits and other similar banking needs at the selected Bank something that could be avoided by using electronic banking facilities. There has been management replacement that was done to bring in new people with new ideas for formulating and drive the service strategies. And high staff turnover at a selected bank is caused by relocation, some employees move to other towns such as Ongwediva while some staff has gone to work for Government. It seems nothing has changed in terms of customer service delivery. According to the Customer Service First website, the customer comment book and Oshiwambo Radio Station between 2013 to 2016 there has been more than 267 complaints registered with the branch concerning the quality of customer services and that warranties any investigation.

A persistent customer complaint is a new phenomenon that requires a responsive approach to address the impact of quality customer service management that is aimed at improving the overall organisational performance. In this study, the researchers have elaborated on the notion of how the quality of customer services is vital to improving the overall organizational performance. This will influence customer perception in trusting the branch service delivery and thus will lead to the total growth of the branch assets and liabilities in relation to sales growth and marketing services for the selected bank in particular. To increase the investment in quality customer service provision, the selected bank top management requires a detailed research that provides in details as to the benefits of quality customer service and the impact it has to the institution and the various stakeholders including the Government.

1.4. Hypotheses and Their Correspondence to Research Design

There have been many customer complaints coming through different media, such as the local indigenous language Radio and Customer Comment Book during the period 2013 to 2016, most of them cited poor customer service as one of the issues that need to be improved. Subsequently, there has been a Management

replacement aimed at improving the situation and many frontline staff were sent to customer service workshops and training however too many customer complaints still do persist. It was not known what really constituted quality customer services and what impact it has on the overall organizational performance. An investigation of the structures in place by the Commercial Bank appears to suggest a system of effective's service delivery and this warrants an investigation that was carried out to fully extract the impact and benefits of quality customer service to the institution and their stakeholders.

The purpose of this study was, therefore to investigate the impact of customer services quality on organizational performance within the scope of social inclusivity. The study aimed at investigating the impact of customer services quality on organizational performance at a selected commercial Bank in Namibia as a social inclusion driver for economic growth within the banking sector. The objectives of the study were:

- To establish the relationship between quality customer service and organisational performance;
- To establish the impact of customer service on organisational performance and
- To offer recommendations to the management and relevant stakeholders

2. Methods

2.1 Identify Subsections

A quantitative research approach was used with a simple random probability sampling. A closed-ended questionnaire was used to collect data to leverage social inclusion through the impact of customer services quality on organizational performance. Fifty-Seven (57) Closed ended-questionnaires were used to collect the data. By using descriptive statistics, data were recorded on excel spreadsheets.

2.2. Participant (Subject) Characteristics

A selected Bank Branch currently has about 20,000 clients registered under the branch categorized as follows as per their income category such as individual queue account holder, saving account holder, Business Cheque account holder. The target population is made up of all the selected commercial Bank clients residing in the Ohangwena Region as defined by the regional boundaries of Namibia. The bank serves clients within the region from smaller towns such as Eenhana, Ondobe, Omafo, Oshikango, Ohangwena, and Engela. Researchers distributed questionnaires to the front liner officials within Oshikango Branch and randomly hand out to individual customers as they enter the branch.

2.3. Sampling Procedure

The sample size process for the questionnaire was 57 participants that were selected using sampling probability simple random sampling techniques who presented themselves at the bank during the period of the survey.

2.4. Sampling Size

A cluster sampling of Fifty Seven 57 participants was simple randomly selected from different account holder categories of clients according to selected commercial bank's classification of clients as well as staff members from the selected commercial Bank branch to enable to make a valued conclusion. A larger sample gave more reliable results, but the response was not 100% of the entire targeted population. Researchers received 70% response from respondents.

2.4.1. Measures and Covariates

A close-ended questionnaire was used to collect data and translated the questions in case of the respondents cannot speak English. A research instrument is a measurement device used by researchers to collect data, of which a 5 Point Likert Scale questionnaire was used for this particular research. The questionnaire was used by the researcher with the closed-ended type of questions.

The questionnaire is a technique whereby all participants are required to respond to a set of similar pre-arranged questions in a set order. Because of its flexibility, a questionnaire is by far the most common instrument used to

collect primary data. The form, wording, and sequence of the questions can influence the responses. Closed-ended questions specify all the possible answers and provide answers that are easier to interpret and tabulate.

The researcher, in this case, used questionnaires because of its flexibility. The researcher administered the questionnaire by the systematic sampling method participants from the selected commercial Bank's clients to the personnel who work directly with customers. The questionnaires with closed-ended questions, which was self-administered in order to ensure a high response rate and allow room for explanations. The primary research instruments of data collection were semi-structured questionnaires used for data collections. Closed-ended questions were the most frequently used in this case study as they allowed respondents to be confined within a certain range of answers by choosing from one or more options.

2.4.2 Research Design

The research method for this research focused only on the collection of textual or visual data. It is generally accepted that it is essential to ensure a tight fit between the purpose or research question and the method. The researcher collected numerical information that is quantifiable and the five intervals were used to collect data as a customer walked into the branch and they provided the researcher with accurate and un-bias information during the data collection. The researchers stand in front of the branch door every morning when it was opening time to hand over questionnaires to five customers on the sequence of five intervals as they walk in the branch.

2.4.3 Experimental

Citing Saunders et al. in his proposal, Changea (2011), states that there is a need to pilot a questionnaire in order to test its validity and effectiveness in bringing about the required result. He continued further by stating that the pilot study also helped to put at ease and prepare participants for the final data collection process.

Pilot studies play an important role in identifying logistical problems which might occur using proposed methods, estimating variability in outcomes to help to determine sample size and collecting preliminary data as well as determining what resources (finance, staff) are needed for a planned study. Researchers carried out a pilot study by distributing 4 questionnaires to the clients (at Eenhana branch and the staff prior to the actual research as this has given him the idea if the questionnaires are properly done. The findings helped the researchers to determine if the questionnaires were extracted the much-needed information from which conclusions can be made, or if the questionnaires require adjustment to cover all the objectives of the study.

3. Results

3.1 Recruitment

The questionnaires were administered at the beginning of December 2016 to first customers who presented themselves in the banking hall during the period of the survey at the selected commercial bank in Namibia. Permission and covering letters explaining what the research was all about to participants were also attached to the questionnaires. Questionnaires were delivered and collected during the period of five days. The personal delivering of questionnaires ensured researcher control by enhancing the collection of the questionnaires. The adoption of personal delivering of questionnaires method increased the overall rate.

3.2 Statistics and Data Analysis

The purpose of data analysis is to build up an empirical model where relationships are carefully brought out so that some meaningful conclusion can be drawn (Shajahan, 2010). For this quantitative study, the researcher followed quantitative analysis in a sequenced account of an experience that is significant to the narrator, indicating a flow of events taken together to convey meaning to the researcher (Saunders et al, 2012).

Collected data were recorded on excel spreadsheets then transferred to SPSS software. The results of the study were presented by using graphs and converting the data into percentage, mean values and percentages.

3.3 Ancillary Analysis

The research instrument used in this research was piloted and through the pilot study, the results convinced

of the reliability of the research instruments. The questionnaire was pre-tested for clarity, completeness, relevance, and shortcomings in a pilot study. Throughout the study, careful considerations were made to ensure the generalizability of findings in terms of the design, measurement and the participants.

One of the strong points of the research instrument developed in this research was the level of consistency it showed regarding items studied during the literature study (Maree, 2016). The statements in the research instruments indicated that the items were discussed in the literature studies that were followed consistently throughout the research instrument to avoid haphazard questioning.

3.4 Participant Flow

The researcher conducted the study for five consecutive days and customers that had challenges in writing or speaking English, the researcher himself translated and filled in the questionnaire to ensure correctness of the data collected.

A cluster sampling of 57 participants was purposefully selected from different account holder categories of clients according to selected commercial Bank's classification of clients as well as staff members from the selected commercial Bank Branch to enable a well-informed conclusion. A larger sample gave more reliable results, but the response was not 100% of the entire targeted population. The researcher received 70% response from respondents.

3.5 Intervention or Manipulation Fidelity

The researcher was available to the research participants in the study at all stages of the research process and answered all questions or concerns. The researcher also made sure not to divulge personal or specific information regarding experiences which might implicate or cause discrimination against anyone for assisting in the research. The researcher at all times reported findings in a complete and honest fashion without misrepresenting. The researcher did not intentionally mislead research participants as to the nature of research findings. Under no circumstances did the researcher fabricated data to support a particular conclusion. The information research participants provided was not made available to anyone who was not directly involved in the study and cannot be traced or identified to the research participants. Observation involves watching what people do, recording, describing, analysing and interpreting the behaviour of the individual or group in order to get a meaningful understanding of the occurrence.

3.6 Baseline Data

The Likert scale was a convenient instrument when the researcher wants to measure a construct. This is accomplished by asking a series of Likert scale questions and then calculating a total score for each respondent, which is assigning the values 1 to 5 depending on how many categories are used.

3.6.1 Statistics and Data Analysis

Maree (2016) states that "quantitative research is a process that systematic and objective in its ways of using numerical data from only a selected subgroup of a universe (or population) to generalize the findings to the universe that is being studied.

While on the other hand, Creswell (2014) argued that quantitative method involve the process of collecting, analysing, interpreting, and writing the results of a study. Specific methods exist in both survey and experimental research that relate to identifying a sample and population, specifying the type of design, collecting and analysing data presenting the results, making an interpretation, and writing the research in a manner consistent with a survey or experimental study. During the late 19th and through the 20th century, strategies of inquiry associated with quantitative research were those that invoked the postpositivist worldview and that originated mainly in psychology. These include true experiments and the less rigorous experiments called quasi-experiments. One type of no experimental quantitative research is casual-comparative research in which the investigator compares two or more groups in terms of a cause (or independent variable) that has already happened. Another no experimental form of research is the correlation design in which investigators use the correlation statistics to describe and measure the degree of association(or relationship)between two or more variables or set of scores (Creswell, 2012).

Moreover, qualitative research takes a particular approach towards the research process, the setting of research questions, the development and use of theory, the choice of research strategy, the way that findings are presented and discussed, and so forth. Overall, qualitative dissertations will be very different

in approach, depending on the particular route that you adopt (e.g., case study research compared to ethnographies). Classic routes that you can follow include auto ethnographies, case study research, ethnographies, grounded theory, narrative research and phenomenological research.

3.6.2 Adverse Events

The Selected Commercial Bank customer service management has been revised every financial year and literature on the quality of customer service and its impact on the overall organisational performance strategies was a major challenge due to the inadequacy of the current similar research done in relation to the topic under study in the bank. Another limitation of this study was the pace of response from the respondents, some wanted to take the questionnaires home and bring it whenever they feel like. The time was too short for a fully employed research who frequently travels all over the country on official engagements to conduct an in-depth study. Participants were ensured by the researchers that, data collected were to be kept confidentially and only used for study purposes. All participants agreed to this research.

4. Discussions

This chapter presents the findings of the research conducted which consist of three subsections; firstly, descriptive results of the research participants' demographic profile are presented. This is followed by the second subsection of the presentation of results of analysed the impact of quality customer service delivery at the selected commercial Bank to the overall organisational performance within the scope of social inclusivity. The third section is the recommendations to management and relevant stakeholders.

Figure 4.1.1 Presentations

It should be noted that not all questions received 100% through 70% of the questionnaires distributed were received. The average of 75% was accepted as a reasonable response that justifies the use of research findings as a basis for making recommendations in this research and this can be supported by Leedy & Ormrod (2017) who defined validity as the extent to which the research findings can be used beyond the study itself. The results of the selected commercial bank Customer profile of research participants included saving account holder, 13 participants were targeted and 6 respondents were obtained representing 46%, current account holder, 14 were targeted and 12 responded were successful representing 85% SME account holder, 15 were targeted and 10 respondents were successful representing 67%, bank Staff of 15 were targeted and all 15 respondent 100% about their experience with selected commercial Bank in Namibia.

4.1.2 Questionnaires Response Analysis

The summary of the questionnaires that were conducted and the response rate are shown below:

Figure 4.1.3 Questionnaire response analyses

The response rate of 67% helps the researchers to do the analysis, conclusions, and recommendations because it timely represents the targeted respondents and thus makes the obtained information very useful in the study. In this section 57 selected commercial bank clients were targeted and 67% of the clients completed a questionnaire, and 2 current account customer was targeted and 1 questionnaire was successful representing 50%, money market account 2 was were targeted and 1 questionnaire was done presenting 50%. Three bank staff were targeted and 2 were successful representing 67% and the total average is 67% response. Also, the results will be enough to make conclusions for the whole group of respondents.

4.2 Findings

When asked whether the customer service impact/contribute to organisational performance there had been a mixed response. Other subjects agree that customer service contribute positively to organisational performance and others did not agree. The frequencies tabulated as follows:

Figure 4.3: Positive impact of the quality of customer service to the organisational performance.

As shown in Figure 4.3 the above (61%) Thirty Four (34) respondents acknowledge that quality customer service contributes mostly towards organisational performance, (6 of the respondents representing 13%) did not acknowledge the importance of customer service to organisational performance, while 3 respondents representing 5% do not know or decline to respond. This means that customer service really contributes positively towards the overall organisational objectives.

Figure 4.4 what was the impact of customer services quality on Commercial Bank’s overall performance?

The Figure 4.4 shows the number of respondents that responded on the impact of service quality on the Commercial Bank operations and they have responded as follows: Seventeen (17) of them representing 39% say the quality of service and its impact on Bank operation is good and 10 respondent representing 23% said the

impact of customer service is bad while on the other hand 11 respondents representing 26% thinks the impact of service quality is very good. Another respondent in a marginal number of 2 = 5% did not respond and other 3 = 7% said the impact of service quality is very bad.

This means a total number of 65% of respondents full agree that, the impact of customer service quality on selected commercial Bank 's overall performance is good; while the average of 30% of the respondents disagree with the notion that, quality customer service does not have an impact on the organisational performance and only 5% abstain to comment.

However, it is important to note that, the general feeling of the respondents has answered the questionnaires judging from the current moment service experience but not necessarily based on the big picture of the quality service impact else were. The findings show a large number of respondents are in agreement with the fact that, the current customer service quality at the selected commercial Bank Oshikango Branch, in particular, has a huge impact on the overall organisational performance. On the other hand, some respondents feel the current service offering reflect a bad customer service quality that has a negative impact on the overall organisational performance.

Figure 4.5. The relationship between customer service quality and how it contributes to organisational performance.

Figure 4.5. depict various service issues and its correlations into Selected Commercial Bank performance and the respondents answered to a greater extent, Less extend, in effect and I do not know. Some of these issues are a customer waiting time which is the highest and customer feel the current turnaround time is unacceptable. Thirty-one (31) respondents =72% feel the more time customer spend in the bank waiting for service has a greater effect on the bank performance. 12 respondents = 28% feel customer bank response after ours has a greater extent while on the other hand, the current bank account notification has 28 respondents = 65% at greater extent and location of the bank has 15 respondents = 34% that feel the location is not that important. Technology has 30 respondents = 70% that says technology affect the bank performance to a greater extent. While layout has 15 respondents =35% and availability of labor has 8 respondents =19% and cash to withdraw has 6 respondents =13% that not really have a big effect on the bank performance.

4.6. Interpretation and Discussion

The previous section presented research results according to research participants' number of customer's profile and research objectives. This section is interpreting and discussing research results according to research objectives.

4.6.1 Research objective 1

This sub-section is interpreting and discussing research results of investigating the quality of customer services at the selected bank. The study revealed that the Bank has difficulties with effective queue management. The researcher is of the view that, the Bank has effective electronic banking services however customer education is needed. The study identified that many customer complaints come as a result of customer understanding and so education is needed to ensure our electronic banking services become fully effective.

The study revealed that majority of customers are happy with the electronic banking services Bank is offering and a minimal number of customers are not happy. The researchers are in agreement that Bank quality customer services have a potential to satisfy the customer demand, however, improvement is required in areas such as queue management, responsiveness, and location of the bank to realise a 100 quality customer services.

The average of 75% was accepted as a reasonable response that justifies the use of research findings as a basis for making recommendations in this research and this can be supported by (Leedy & Orman, 2017) defined validity as the extent to which the research findings apply to a situation beyond the study itself. The results of Bank Customer profile of research participants included saving account holder, 13 participants were targeted and 6 respondents were obtained representing 46%, current account holder, 14 were targeted and 12 responded were successful representing 85% SME account holder, 15 were targeted and 10 respondents were successful representing 67%, Bank Staff of 15 were targeted and all 15 respondent 100% about their experience with the selected Bank. Cook (2011: 17) explained that most people define service Excellency based on personal experience. The garage which unexpectedly provides complimentary umbrellas to its customers when they come to collect their cars and it's raining, the newsagent who gives the customer a free sweet when they come to pay their newspaper bill –these would be seen by many as good service.

Mohanty & Lakhe (2011: 49) narrated that most service quality definitions are customer led and have an external focus. Quality is defined as consistently meeting or exceeding customer expectations. This approach relies on the ability of the organization to determine customer requirements and then meet these requirements. A customer led definition implicitly encompasses the supply-led approach. This is because the customer's requirements are built into the service at the design stage, but it is at the transformation stage that the degree of conformance is determined. This approach, therefore, is suitable for organizations offering high contract skill and knowledge-based or labour-intensive services such as healthcare, law, education, and leisure and hotel ring.

It is also safe to contrast this theory in relation to service excellence that is associated with the quality service. He further stressed that, in all industries, some organization is more profitable than others irrespective of the industry's average profitability.

4.6.2 Research Objective 2

This sub-section is interpreting and discussing research results as to establish the impact of customer services on organisational performance. When asked whether the customer service impact/contribute to organisational performance there had been a mixed response. Other subjects agree that customer service contribute positively to organisational performance and others did not agree.

A large number of 20 respondents representing 46% are banking with Bank because of the electronic banking facilities that include, cell phone banking, the point of sale and both business and personal online banking. Another group of respondents of 8 representing 19% is banking with the selected commercial bank for easy access to ATMs and more branches across every town in the country. While on the other hand, 7 respondents representing 16% remain with Bank for Innovation offering the selected commercial Bank have in place and the

5 equal to 11% of the respondents like Bank brand, while only 3 respondents = 16% do not know why they are banking with Bank.

4.6.3 Research Objective 3

To offer recommendations to the management of the organization and relevant stakeholders.

The researchers recommend to the top management of selected commercial Bank to keep on investing in the customer service as it contributes to overall organizational performance. Investment in customer service will help Selected Commercial Bank branch retain and attract more customers yielding much-needed profitability for the financial institution.

The researchers recommend that selected commercial Bank to introduce more ATMs across the Business Centers of Oshikango to provide more banking services alternatives to Customers that will lead to the reduction of long queues in the branch and so enhance the customer service quality. Part of the quality customer service delivery efforts and transparency the bank should provide notifications to all bank charges as more customer visit the bank for bank charges inquiries that lead to long queues and that can be reduced by introducing the cell phone notifications like other big transactions. E-wallet to be more flexible to be accessible to other banks, Mobile ATM should be made available at newly proclaimed Settlements, dedicated Home loan consultant for the region, More shops need Slim lines.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that there is a strong relationship between customer service and organisational performance. The more an organisation invests in its customer service the better their chances of outperforming their competitors. Organisations that do not invest much in customer service will also not improve in terms of performance of the company financially or through meeting its objectives and mission. There are few respondents who still do not recognize the importance and positive impact of customer service on organisational performance.

The researchers also further concluded that the selected commercial Bank just like other financial institutions as well the general business community need to invest much in customer service as they will yield them a better return on their customer service investments. It is also concluded that though many participants believed customer service to be of vital role to organisational performance while only a “handful” of participants did not agree with the idea, Selected Commercial Bank might need to carry out a similar research from another different branch for the purpose of comparison of the findings and conclusions as well as recommendations.

Recommendations

The following are recommendations to selected commercial Bank Namibia on the management of Oshikango Branch initiatives that can be adopted to improve the quality of customer service.

The researchers recommend to the top management of selected commercial Bank to keep on investing in the customer service as it contributes to overall organizational performance. Investment in customer service will help selected commercial Bank branch retain and attract more customers yielding much-needed profitability for the financial institution.

The researchers recommend that selected commercial Bank to introduce more ATMs across the Business Centers of Oshikango to provide more banking services alternatives to Customers that will lead to the reduction of long queues in the branch and so enhance the customer service quality. Part of the quality customer service delivery efforts and transparency the bank should provide notifications to all bank charges as more customer visit the bank for bank charges inquiries that lead to long queues and that can be reduced by introducing the cell phone notifications like other big transactions. E-wallet to be more flexible to be accessible to other banks,

Mobile ATM should be made available at all newly proclaimed Settlements, dedicated Home loan consultant for the region, More shops need Slim lines. The bank should introduce more mobile ATM and clear and easy banking instructions that are easy to read in local languages.

The researchers recommend for business coaching desk to provide training to the development of SMEs in the region. In line with the quality customer service improvement, it is further recommended that selected commercial Bank visited Branch should expand the customer banking hall with the provision of sitting spaces for all clients.

The researchers further recommend that Commercial Bank should not only rely on the results of this study to make investment decisions alone. The financial institution and other business organisations are recommended to adopt other methods to establish the relationship between the quality of customer service and organisational performance in line with a Namibian true spirit of Harambee Prosperity Plan and National Development Goals that compels every organisation in both public and private sector to improve customer service delivery. The financial institutions just like other organisations can adopt methods such as the Return on Investment (ROI) whereby they can calculate their output or income generated as compared to what they have invested in it. This can be done by comparing the budget for customer service against the revenue generated during that period. A cost-benefit analysis can also be carried out to find the relationship between customer service and organizational performance. Performance can be in terms of profitability of in terms of achieving the purpose of the organization.

It is also further advised that Selected Commercial Bank just like other financial institutions and business organisations should invest in Research and Development (R&D) as well as marketing research to be fully aware of customer expectations. It is only through research that customer needs will be met. Meeting and exceeding customer expectations amounts to proper customer service as well as establishing relationships with customers rather than a transaction with them.

The researcher also suggests other research be carried out similar to this to establish the relationship between customer service and organisational performance. This will help in clearly coming to a solid conclusion if an independent research is carried out in another sector different from the banking industry to establish the same results.

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